

First teratological case of *Pseudomyrmex termitarius* (Smith, 1855) (Hymenoptera: Formicidae: Pseudomyrmecinae)

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Abstract

A case of abnormalities in segmentation (symphysomery) on the metasoma in a worker ant of the species *Pseudomyrmex termitarius* (Smith, 1855) is described for the first time from Colombia. In the abnormal metasoma, the petiole and postpetiole are fused, and the number of segments of the opisthogaster is reduced. For taxonomic studies, these kinds of abnormalities can generate confusion when identifying individuals at the genus and species levels. For an individual, an anatomical abnormality might affect its biology and interaction with other individuals inside its social insect colony.

Keywords

Abnormality, ants, symphysomery, metasoma, segments

Introduction

Teratology is the science that studies the causes, mechanisms, and patterns of abnormal development in plants and animals (Ujházy et al. 2012). In insects, morphological anomalies may be partial (cephalic, thoracic, abdominal, atrophies, heterochronies, and heteromorphoses) or total (gigantism, dwarfism, asymmetry, gynandromorphism, and intersexuality) (Balazuc 1948).

The different types of morphological abnormalities that occur in insects, particularly in Hymenoptera (bees, ants, and wasps), were described by Balazuc (1958). Recently, several teratological cases have been recorded in Hymenoptera (Turrisi et al. 2022; Can 2022; Can and Ruchin 2024; Pérez-Lachaud et al. 2024; Cambra et al. 2025).

In Formicidae, perhaps the best-known and most well-studied type of teratology is gynandromorphy (Wheeler 1903; Donisthorpe 1929; Wheeler 1937; Buschinger and Stoewesand 1971; Cokendolpher and Francke 1983; Jones and Phillips 1985; Scupola 1994). Gynandromorphy is an anomaly that results in an organism that presents both male and female phenotypes (Krichilsky et al. 2020).

Regarding abnormalities in segmentation, previous studies have recorded abnormalities in the abdominal segments of 14 species of ants of the genera *Camponotus* Mayr, 1861 (Formicinae); *Diacamma* Mayr, 1862 (Ponerinae); *Formica* Linnaeus, 1758 (Formicinae); *Leptothorax* Mayr, 1855 (Myrmicinae); *Myrmica* Latreille, 1804 (Myrmicinae); and *Oecophylla* Smith, 1860 (Formicinae) (Forel 1901; Viehmeyer 1917; Forel 1920; Donisthorpe 1922; Creighton 1928; Gosswald 1932; Záleský 1938; Weber 1946; Sweeney 1950).

During regular curation procedures at Laboratorio de Entomología Universidad de la Amazonia (LEUA) in Florencia, Caquetá, Colombia, a specimen of *Pseudomyrmex termitarius* (Smith, 1855) (Hymenoptera: Formicidae: Pseudomyrmecinae) was observed with its petiole and postpetiole fused and its gaster reduced. Accordingly, the aim of this study is to present a new record of teratology observed in the metasomal segments of a worker ant of the species *P. termitarius*.

Materials and methods

As part of the MSc thesis project of the first author related to *Pseudomyrmex* in Colombia, a liquid sample composed of 10 worker ant individuals was found at Museo Javeriano de Historia Natural (MPUJ) in Bogotá, D.C. The sample was relocated to the LEUA for curation and taxonomic study. Specimens were identified as *Pseudomyrmex termitarius* (Smith, 1855) using the taxonomic key for the *Pseudomyrmex* species from Colombia published by Ward (2019). Among the individuals studied, one was registered as showing abnormalities compared to the others.

The measurements performed and the indices calculated to confirm the identity of the species *Pseudomyrmex termitarius* are based on Ward (2017) and include:

HW: head width, HL: head length, EL: eye length, MFC: minimum frontal carinal distance, SL: scape length, FL: profemur length, FW: profemur width, PL: petiole length, PH: petiole height, DPW: dorsal petiole width, LHT: metatibia length, CI: cephalic index (HW/HL), REL: relative eye length (EL/HL), REL2: relative eye length (EL/HW), FCI: frontal carinal index (MFC/HW), SI: scape index (SL/HW), FI: profemur index (FW/FL), PLI: petiole length index (PH/PL), PWI: petiole width index (DPW/PL), MSC: mesosomal setal count, HTC: metatibial setal count, and MTC: mesotibial setal count. All linear measurements are in millimeters.

Images and measurements of the specimens (worker ants) of *P. termitarius* included in this work were taken using a LEICA M205A stereomicroscope and a HITACHI TM4000Plus II environmental scanning electron microscope. All figures were prepared utilizing the software Photoshop 2023 v. 24.0.

Results

Material examined. COLOMBIA • 10 worker ants; Tolima, Coello, Reserva El Neme, 1 km SW de Coello; 4°16'N, 74°54'W; 09 Mar. 2015; Niño "leg. "; Malaise trap in open vegetation stubble; MPUJ.

Identification. Worker caste specimens of *Pseudomyrmex termitarius* are recognized by the following characters according to Kempf (1960): "MEASUREMENTS: Total length 6.1–7.3 mm; head length 1.18–1.46 mm; head width 1.16–1.39 mm; thorax length 1.68–2.14 mm. Indices: cephalic: 93–100; oculo-cephalic 55–62; cephalo-thoracic 68–73; thoracic 37–42. COLORATION: Color variable. Head and gaster apical segments blackish, thorax and petiole ferruginous or testaceous brown. Scape and legs between black and light brown. Thorax dorsal aspect darkened. STRUCTURE: Head rather subcircular than longitudinally elliptical. Mandibles with fine longitudinal striations; basal tooth not retracted. Anterior edge of the clypeus median lobe beveled in the middle, with the lateral angles subacute. Interocular distance greater than eyes length. Pronotum scapular angles marked and prominent; lateral edges bordered with a strong keel, little converging backward, almost straight; dorsal aspect convex. Mesonotum and epinotum basal face, seen in profile, in the same plane, not forming an angle. Mid-epinotal suture absent, replaced by slight transverse impression. Epinotum basal aspect with weak lateral margination, its length equal to that of the slope face. Petiole beaded, semi-peduncle anterior, compressed from side to side, with a dorsal aspect marginata on each side, like posterior angles protruding and clearly marginalized. Petiole ventral aspect with anterior quite robust. VESTITURE: Setae 1 supra-ocular, 1 scapular, 1 postero-lateral not post-petiole. Pubescence sericeous and tiny, clearly visible on the gaster, less on the rest of the body, unless under high pressure. Gaster with bristles raised and abundant."

Anatomical characteristics of normal specimens of *Pseudomyrmex termitarius* are presented in Figs 1A, B, and 2A–D. Measurements and indices for the nine normal specimens studied are included in Table 1.

Figure 1. Specimens of *Pseudomyrmex termitarius* (worker cast). **A–B.** Normal specimen. **A** – Habitus, dorsal view. **B** – Habitus, lateral view. **C–D.** Abnormal specimen. **C** – Habitus, dorsal view. **D** – Habitus, lateral view.

Description of teratology

Abnormal segmentation of the metasoma. Petiole and postpetiole fused (Fig. 2E), so the anatomical structure is subsquare (lateral view), subrectangular (dorsal view) with dorsal aspect rounded, ventroanterior and ventroposterior aspects with subtriangular and angled processes (lateral view) (Fig. 2G). Opisthogaster cordate (dorsal view), length less than mesosoma length (lateral view), tergites I, II, and III large, visible, and equal in length; pygidium with hairs as long as petiole length (Fig. 2F, H). Anatomical characteristics of abnormal specimens of *Pseudomyrmex termitarius* are presented in Figs 1C, D, and 2E–H. Measurements and indices for one abnormal specimen studied are included in Table 1.

Table 1. Measurements (mm) and indices of 10 specimens (worker caste) of *Pseudomyrmex termitarius*

	Normal specimens (n=9)											Abnormal specimen (n=1)
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Min	Max	1
HW	1.26	1.30	1.26	1.29	1.27	1.27	1.29	1.27	1.27	1.26	1.30	1.21
HL	1.26	1.26	1.23	1.28	1.28	1.26	1.27	1.26	1.26	1.23	1.28	1.20
EL	0.75	0.77	0.77	0.79	0.78	0.77	0.76	0.77	0.77	0.75	0.79	0.73
MFC	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04
SL	0.63	0.62	0.63	0.62	0.62	0.63	0.63	0.62	0.63	0.62	0.63	0.58
FL	0.93	0.91	0.92	0.94	0.91	0.92	0.93	0.92	0.92	0.91	0.93	0.91
FW	0.37	0.37	0.36	0.37	0.35	0.37	0.36	0.37	0.36	0.36	0.37	0.35
PL	0.65	0.67	0.66	0.67	0.63	0.66	0.66	0.65	0.67	0.65	0.67	0.56*
PH	0.41	0.42	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.42	0.42	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.43	0.44*
DPW	0.38	0.36	0.36	0.37	0.38	0.38	0.38	0.37	0.38	0.36	0.38	0.40*
LHT	1.16	1.05	1.09	1.10	1.14	1.10	1.12	1.14	1.14	1.05	1.16	1.11
CI	1.00	1.03	1.02	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.01	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.03	1.00
REL	0.59	0.61	0.62	0.61	0.60	0.61	0.59	0.61	0.61	0.59	0.61	0.60
REL2	0.59	0.59	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.60	0.58	0.60	0.60	0.58	0.61	0.60
FCI	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
SI	0.50	0.47	0.50	0.48	0.48	0.49	0.48	0.48	0.49	0.47	0.49	0.47
FI	0.39	0.40	0.40	0.39	0.38	0.40	0.38	0.40	0.39	0.38	0.40	0.38
PLI	0.63	0.62	0.65	0.64	0.68	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.61	0.61	0.68	0.78*
PWI	0.58	0.53	0.54	0.55	0.60	0.57	0.55	0.56	0.56	0.53	0.60	0.71*
MSC	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
HTC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MTC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Note: * Variables measured for fused petiole and postpetiole.

Figure 2. Specimens of *Pseudomyrmex termitarius* (worker caste). A–D. Metasoma, normal specimen. A – Petiole and postpetiole, dorsal view. B – Opisthogaster, lateral view. Continued on the next page.

Figure 2. Continued from the previous page. **C** – Petiole and postpetiole, lateral view, SEM. **D** – Opisthogaster, lateral view, SEM. **E–H.** Metasoma, abnormal specimen. **E** – Petiole and postpetiole fused, dorsal view. **F** – Opisthogaster, lateral view. **G** – Petiole and postpetiole fused, lateral view, SEM. **H** – Opisthogaster, lateral view, SEM.

Discussion

Workers ants of the genus *Pseudomyrmex* are recognized by having twelve antennomeres, three conspicuous ocelli (very noticeable), elongated eyes (width two-thirds or less than length), mandibles with proximal tooth on the basal margin, one petiole, one postpetiole, and a stinger (Ward 1985, 1990). However, one of the specimens examined presents a segmentation abnormality in the metasoma, characterized by the fusion of the petiole and postpetiole and a reduced gaster.

In the 10 specimens studied, the length of the fused petiole and postpetiole is shorter in the abnormal specimen than the petiole length of normal ants. In contrast, the height and width of the fused petiole and postpetiole have higher values in the abnormal specimen than in normal ants. The opisthogaster has five visible segments in the normal specimens, while it only has three in the abnormal specimen.

Segmentation abnormalities occur during the embryonic phase and their origin may be genetic issues, changes in the hormone system or external stimuli (biological, chemical, mechanical, or physical) (Balazuc 1958; Ćurčić and Dimitrijević 1982; Sander 1988; Ornosá et al. 1998; Trabalón et al. 2000). Among the segmentation anomalies, symphysomery is a condition in which there is partial or total fusion of two segments (Balazuc, 1948).

Furthermore, the abnormal specimen presents lower values in measurements such as HW, HL, EL, and SL than the range presented by the normal specimens studied from the same colony. However, the HW and HL measurements are within the range established in the description for *P. termitarius*, included in Kempf (1960).

The teratology case observed in *P. termitarius* highlights the relevance of studying structural anomalies in social insects from a taxonomic perspective. The anomalous metasoma could alter the typical diagnosis of the genus and species, and an individual with this condition could taxonomically be classified incorrectly.

From a functional point of view, abnormalities in the metasoma could affect the mobility, food storage capacity, and defense of the individual, fundamental aspects for *Pseudomyrmex* caste workers. Since workers are mainly responsible for foraging and colony care tasks, any limitation in their performance could alter the social dynamics and effectiveness of the group. This is especially important in the context of social species, where cooperation is essential for collective survival.

Teratological cases of individuals within a population probably have implications for the ecology of communities. For example, a worker ant with reduced capacities could alter the competition dynamics or mutualism in the food webs where *P. termitarius* participates.

Conclusions

A new record of teratology in the metasomal segments of a worker ant of the species *Pseudomyrmex termitarius* (Smith, 1855) is presented. This study highlights the need to expand efforts to document cases of teratology in insects, especially in biodiverse regions such as Colombia. The reported case of symphysomery in *P. termitarius* stands out not only as a morphological curiosity but as an opportunity to learn about the biological and ecological implications it brings for the abnormal individual and the others in the colony of social species. Moreover, the combination of modern imaging techniques and morphometric analyses, such as those used in this work, allows the precise characterization of the anomalies and facilitates their comparison with previously documented cases.

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